

genes for bacterial blight (BB), rice blast (Bl), and brown planthopper (BPH).

Two early rice varieties with medium growth duration—Xiang Zaoxian 3 and

HA793 17-4—have been selected from segregating material of IR36/ Guong jie 9. They have resistance to BB, Bl, BPH, and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH),

and high yield (see table). By 1987, they had been planted in 500,000 ha in Hubei, Jiangxi, Guongxi, and Zhejiang Provinces. □

Three rice varieties named in Ghana

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In Ghana, rice is cultivated mostly under rainfed conditions.

C168 from the cross Intan/BPI-76-1 from the Philippines, IR1750-F5-B5 from the cross E425/IR22 from IIRI, and ToX 516-19-Sel from the cross Moroberekan/ Juma I, ToX 7-3-2-3-2, and SE3639 from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) were selected from IRTP trials early in the 1980s.

They consistently have outyielded most other varieties and local checks under rainfed lowland shallow conditions at research sites (Table 1). Even in 1983, with a Jun-Oct growing season rainfall of only 497 mm at Nyankpala and 547 mm at Manga, compared to the 30-yr average 785 mm and 794 mm, yields equaled or were higher than those of the check varieties.

On-farm test yields in 1985 and 1986 also were encouraging (Table 2), and in 1987 the Ghana Rice Varietal Release Committee accepted GR19 (C168), GR20 (IR1750-F5-B5), and GR21 (ToX 516-19-Sel) for rainfed cultivation.

GR19 (100 cm tall) matures in about 120 d; GR20 (90 cm), in 105 d; and GR21 (90 cm), in 110 d. All have acceptable cooking and eating qualities and are resistant or moderately resistant to leaf blast and brown spot. □

Table 1. Grain yield and reactions to blast and brown spot of GR19, GR20, and GR21 under rainfed conditions at research sites in Ghana, 1981-85.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)					Reaction ^a to		
	1981 (1 site)	1982 (2 sites)	1983 ^a (2 sites)	1984 (3 sites)	1985 (9 sites)	Mean ^b	Blast	Brown spot
GR19 (C168)	3.8	2.1	1.2	2.6	2.0	2.3 (46%)	2	3
GR20 (IR1750-F5-B5)	4.4	2.4	1.6	1.7	2.1	2.4 (53%)	3	2
GR21 (ToX 516-19-Sel)	4.4	2.4	1.0	2.8	2.5	2.6 (65%)	3	3
Check variety Tamale 1	2.4	1.4	1.0	1.4	1.8	1.6	7	5

^aRainfall deficit was 247-288 mm at trial sites. ^bPercentages show yield increase over check variety. ^cBy the *Standard evaluation systems for rice* scale.

Table 2. On-farm trial grain yield of GR19, GR20, and GR21 in Ghana, 1985 and 1986.

Site	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	GR19	GR21	GR20	Local check
	1985			
Nayoko	2.6	2.8	2.9	1.7
Zawse	2.2	2.8	2.8	1.6
Zabgo	0.9	1.7	2.3	2.2
Gore	0.4	0.6	1.3	0.5
Vane	3.4	4.9	2.7	2.8
Mean	1.9	2.6	2.4	1.8
	1986			
Tarkpaa 1	2.2	2.4		1.3
Tarkpaa 2	2.9	1.8		2.1
Tarkpaa 3	1.7	1.2		0.8
Cheshegu	2.4	2.2		1.4
Zuarungu	3.7	^a		2.9
Soe 1	0.9	0.8		0.7
Soe 2	5.2	5.2		5.6
Bladjei	1.5	1.6		1.1
Katiejeli	0.9	0.6		1.3
Tarkpaa 4	3.0	3.1		3.0
Kete Krachi	2.9	3.5		3.8
Kpassa/Nkwanta	^a	3.3		1.4
Central Volta	2.6	2.9		1.0
Gbefi	3.3	3.9		1.2
Vane	^a	2.3		2.0
Mean	2.6	2.5		2.0

^aNot included.

Red Triveni, a promising short-duration variety for India

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Of three short-duration, semidwarf, high-yielding rice varieties released in Kerala, Triveni is the most popular among Kerala farmers. Farmers who have a strong preference for red grain have been asking for a red-grained version, adaptable to all growing seasons.

About 5 yr after Triveni's release, a few isolated red-grained plants were found. Red-grained plants reoccurred, despite strict roguing.

White-grained PTB15, one of the parents in the evolution of Triveni, has purple tipping. Possibly, segregation for